

ANXIETY AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL PUPILS WITH PHYSICAL DISABILITY

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Abstract

Anxiety is a normal human emotion that everyone experiences at times. It is a cognitive emotional process that occurs in most people. Many people feel anxious, when faced with a problem at their work, before taking a test, or making an important decision. Anxiety is one of the factors, which are responsible for students' performance, but it can be managed by appropriate training of students in dealing with factors causing anxiety.

The present study aims to investigate the level of anxiety among high school children with physical disability. A total of hundred 9th class pupils were selected from different schools in Guntur district by adapting the simple random technique. A standardized tool was used to obtain response from the students. The survey method is considered to be the best method for the present study. Mean, % of mean, SD calculations were done. The result of the study showed that boys have high anxiety than the girls.

Key Words: *Anxiety, Emotions and Physical Disability.*

Introduction

Anxiety is one of the most studied phenomena's in psychology. It is normal human response to stress. The concept of anxiety is differentiated from fear as it is a normal human response to stress. Today anxiety is a common phenomenon of everyday life. It plays a crucial role in human life because all of us are victim of anxiety in different ways (Goodstein and Lanyon, 1975).

Anxiety is an essential, physical response that communicates the need to pay attention to something in the environment. It starts as a biochemical change in our brain and body with the release of adrenalin. Anxiety, also called angst or worry, is a psychological and physiological state characterized by somatic, emotional, cognitive and behavioural components. The root meaning of the word anxiety is vex or trouble; in either presence or

absence of psychological stress, anxiety and create feelings of fear, worry, uneasiness and dread. At a lower level, anxiety helps individuals to deal with a difficult situation by prompting them to cope up with it but when anxiety becomes excessive, it becomes a disorder.

Meaning

Anxiety is a state of mind in response to some stimulus in the environment which brings in the feelings of apprehension or fear.

Anxiety disorders are a group of mental disorders characterized by feelings of anxiety and fear, where anxiety is a worry about future events and fear is a reaction to current events. These feelings may cause physical symptoms, such as a racing heart and shakiness. There are various forms of anxiety disorders, including generalized anxiety disorder, phobic disorder, and panic disorder. While each has its own characteristics and symptoms, they all include symptoms of anxiety.

The term handicapped, when used in a wider sense, include intellectual disabilities and disadvantages which are cause learning hardship. In the light of the above discussion, the study will look into the various learning hardship likely to be faced by the handicapped child in school. Previous researchers have revealed that behaviours are judged in terms of the society existing standards, therefore the ability of the handicapped can be under estimated by their teacher because already they are termed that they cannot perform as well as the naturally endowed pupils/students. This study will examine the various problems facing the education of the handicaps ones.

Some children are physically handicapped from birth, others develop infirmities after accidents. There are many physical disabilities like blindness, lameness, deafness, dumbness etc. There are other children, who may not have any physical abnormalities, but they might be abnormally short, fat, with jutting teeth, small and sunken eyes and several such features.

A physically handicapped person is defined as a person who has a disability of locomotor and neurological origin which constitutes a disadvantage or restriction in one or more aspects of daily living activities, including work.

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Significance of the Study

The problem of anxiety occupies a central position in the theory of psycho-pathology and psychosomatic dysfunctions. Stated briefly, anxiety is the signal of danger which mobilizes the human organisms resources at all levels of functioning in the interest of conservation, defense and self-preservation. Yet, it is also the sign of disorganization which in large quantities leads only to further disturbance and regression of functioning. At all levels of anxiety there are various combinations in degree of loss of homeostatic control and attempts at mastery to re-gain control.

The present day terrible competition, graving for marks and ranks are the major factor. That is increasing anxiety in every body. Unless the anxiety levels are brought down and concentered into positive direction the present student generation cannot cope up. Therefore it is the need of ours and the responsibility of teachers to look into the anxiety levels of their students and analyze the situation thoroughly and think and adopt the remedies.

Review of Related Literature

Anita Karki (2022) conduct a study on ‘Depression, anxiety and stress among high school students: A cross-sectional study in an urban municipality of Kathmandu, Nepal’, reveals that more than half of the students had depression and anxiety symptoms.

R. Kranti Kumar (2022) conduct a study on ‘The prevalence of depression, anxiety, and stress among high school adolescent's children in public and private schools in Rangareddy district Telangana state: A cross-sectional study’ found that the prevalence of anxiety in children from public schools was 20.8% and in private schools was 20.5%.

Shahnawaz Mushtaq (2016) studied on ‘Self Esteem, Anxiety, Depression and Stress among Physically Disabled People’; found that physically disabled people have low level of self-esteem and high level of depression, stress and anxiety in comparison to normal population.

Sr. Kaula Assumpta Syokwaa (2014) conduct a study ‘The Relationship between Anxiety Levels and Academic Achievement among Students in Selected Secondary Schools’ in Lang’ata District, Kenya, found that high personality anxiety levels at 79%, while the test anxiety indicated a relatively low-normal anxiety level of 27%.

Objectives

1. To study the level of anxiety among secondary school pupils with physical disability.
2. To study the level of anxiety among secondary school pupils with physical disability with respect to the following variables:

- Gender : Boy / Girl

- Locality : Rural/ Urban
- Type of Institute : Government / Private

Hypotheses

1. There would be significant difference in the anxiety levels of physically disabled pupils with respect to Gender.
2. There would be no significant difference in the anxiety levels of physically disabled pupils with respect to Locality.
3. There would be no significant difference in the anxiety levels of physically disabled pupils with respect to Type of Institution.

Delimitations of the Study

- Due to several constraints the present study was limited to the secondary school pupils with physical disability in Guntur District only.
- The study is limited to 100 secondary school pupils of Guntur district only.

Method

For the present study normative survey method is used.

Sample and Sampling

Random sample of 100 secondary school pupils with physical disability were chosen from Guntur district only.

Tool of the Study

A standardized questionnaire Test Anxiety Inventory (TAI; Spielberger et al., 1980) was used in the present study to measure the anxiety levels of secondary school students. It consists 20-item self-report measure using a 4-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (almost never) to 4 (almost always), in which higher scores indicate higher levels of test anxiety. 4-point Likert scale (1–4) yielding a total test anxiety score ranging from 20 to 80 points.

Reliability and Validity of the Tool

Reliability is the consistency of a test yielding the same results in measuring, whether it does measure i.e. consistency throughout the series of measurement. Which has got internal coefficient contending. The reliability was found to be 0.72 which indicates the questionnaire was reliable.

Scoring Criteria

The scoring criteria are three alternate responses Always, Sometimes and Never.

Table 1

Item	Always	Sometimes	Never
For positive items	2	1	0
For negative items	0	1	2

Statistical Techniques Used

Mean, SD, % of Mean and 't' value are to be calculated.

Data Analysis**Objective – 1**

To study the level of anxiety among high school children with physical disability.

Table 2 - Anxiety Levels of 9th standard Physical Challenged Pupils

Sample	Mean	S.D	% of Mean
100	34.78	5.58	67.18

Interpretation

The above table whole sample mean is 34.78% of mean is 67.18 and their SD is 5.58 respectively. From the above table the mean scores of anxiety levels of physically disabled pupils is moderate.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference in the anxiety levels of physically disabled pupils with respect to Gender.

Table 3 - Anxiety Levels of Physical Disabled Boys and Girls

Gender	Sample size	Mean	S.D	S.Ed	't' value
Boys	60	32.18	5.46	0.76	1.65 NS
Girls	40	30.92	5.31		

NS= Not significant at 0.05 level

Interpretation

The calculated 't' value is 1.65 is less than the table value 1.96. There is no significant difference between boy and girl students in their anxiety levels. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted. The boys mean value is greater than the girls mean value hence the anxiety levels of physically challenged boys have high anxiety than the girls.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference in the anxiety levels of 9th standard physical challenged pupils with respect to locality

Table 4 - Anxiety Levels of Rural and Urban Physical Disabled Pupils

Locality	Sample size	Mean	S.D	S.Ed	't' value
Rural	50	33.71	5.10		
Urban	50	31.49	5.21	0.72	3.08*

*- Significant at 0.05 level and 0.01 level

Interpretation

The calculated 't' value is 3.08 greater than the table value. There is significant difference between rural and urban school students in their anxiety levels. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected. It could also be concluded that the rural pupils are having more anxiety levels than the urban pupils.

Hypothesis 3

There is no significant difference in the anxiety levels physical disabled pupils with respect to Type of Institute.

Table 5 - Anxiety Levels of Govt. and Private Physical Disabled Pupils

Type of the Institute	Sample size	Mean	S.D.	S.Ed	't' value
Govt.	50	32.87	5.47		
Private	50	30.91	5.32	0.766	1.644NS

NS= Not significant at 0.05 level

Interpretation

The calculated 't' value is 1.644 greater than the table value 1.96. There is no significant difference between govt. and private high school students with physical disability in their anxiety levels. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted.

Findings

- In table 2 the whole sample mean is 34.78 % of mean is 67.18 and their SD is 5.58 respectively.
- The mean scores of anxiety levels of physical disabled boys are greater than the girls. Boys have high anxiety than the girls.
- There is significant difference between rural and urban high school pupils with physical disability in their anxiety levels.
- There is no significant difference between government and private school physically disabled pupils in their anxiety levels.

Suggestions

- Teachers should adopt the strategies to decrease the level of anxiety.

- We can reduce level of academic anxiety among students by appropriate training and if the evaluation system is student friendly.

Conclusion

Knowledge about academic anxiety is of immense worth both for teachers and learners and it will play an important role in teaching-learning process. The present study has its implication for parents, teachers, policy makers, administrators, central and state government, and all other bodies related to the development of the students at high school stage directly and indirectly.

References

- Anita Karki (2022) *Depression, anxiety and stress among high school students: A cross-sectional study in an urban municipality of Kathmandu, Nepal*, Nepal. *PLOS Glob Public Health* 2(5): e0000516. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pgph.0000516>
- Barlow, David H. (2000), *Unrevealing the mysteries of anxiety and its disorders from the perspective of emotion theory*. *American Psychologist* 55 (11): 1247-63.
- Gaudry and Spielberger (1972). *Test anxiety differences in boys and girls in relation to their academic achievement*. *Journal of instructional psychology: A psychological abstract*.
- Koul, Lokesh (2004): *Methodology of Educational Research*, Vikas Publishing House Pvt Ltd 576, Masjid Road, Jangpura, New Delhi-110014.
- R. Kranti Kumar (2022) *'The prevalence of depression, anxiety, and stress among high school adolescent's children in public and private schools in Rangareddy district Telangana state: A cross-sectional study'* *Journal of Education and Health Promotion* (Vol.11, PMID: 355773619).
- Shahnawaz Mushtaq (2016), *Self Esteem, Anxiety, Depression and Stress among Physically Disabled People*, *The International Journal of Indian Psychology* (ISSN 2348-5396 (e) | ISSN: 2349-3429 (p) Volume 3, Issue 4, pp.125).
- Neelam and Attri, A.K. (2013), *Academic Anxiety and Achievement of Secondary School Students*, *International Journal of Behavioral Social and Movement Sciences* (Vol. 02- Issue 1, pp. 27).
- Singh, B. (2003). *A Study of Anxiety among Medical Post Graduate Students in relation to Sex, Intelligence and Socio-Economic Status*, *Indian Educational Review* (Vol. 39, No. 2, pp.90).